

ELIXIR Commissioned Service - Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP), Computational Resource Allocation Tool Development

M3.1 Prototype and metadata of Galaxy workflow

Tier: Science

Priority Area: Biodiversity, Food Security, and Pathogens (BFSP)

Executive Summary

A prototype of the optimized workflow for constructing Metagenome-Assembled Genomes (MAGs) was successfully developed and initially made available on UseGalaxy Europe. The required metadata—such as licence, creators, and annotations—was added to ensure proper documentation and attribution. This milestone has since been superseded by D3.1, “Workflow available on UseGalaxy Europe and UseGalaxy France servers as well as published on IWC and WorkflowHub”, which includes the relevant links for accessing and disseminating the workflow. While this milestone laid the groundwork for the current deliverable, links to the original prototype are no longer relevant following the workflow’s formal publication in the IWC, which it helped to enable.

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Supporting Documents

See D3.1

Dissemination Plans

See D3.1